

The Influence of U.S. Monetary Policy Uncertainty and Inflation Expectations on the Economy of Puerto Rico: Insights from a VAR Model

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Research Article

Abstract

This paper investigates the relationship between Puerto Rico's Headline CPI Inflation Rate, Unemployment Rate, U.S. monetary policy uncertainty, and inflation expectations using a VAR model based on the methodology of Toda and Yamamoto (1995), covering the period 1985–2024. Results reveal bi-directional Granger causality between Puerto Rico's macroeconomic indicators and U.S. inflation expectations, but not with monetary policy uncertainty. Impulse responses and variance decompositions highlight the significant influence of U.S. inflation expectations on Puerto Rico's inflation and unemployment. The findings underscore the island's macroeconomic sensitivity to U.S. expectations.

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1. Introduction

As an unincorporated territory of the United States of America (US), Puerto Rico is integrated into the US customs system. This relationship establishes the island and the continental US as a unified market characterized by free trade dynamics (Martínez and Rivera, 2005). Another significant institutional consequence of this political relationship is Puerto Rico's lack of a central bank, as the territory operates within the US financial system (Kicinski, 2002; Rodríguez, 2016). Consequently, Puerto Rico is part of the Second District of the Federal Reserve System, allowing capital to flow freely between the island and the continent (Bram et al., 2008). Additionally, scholars have argued that this relationship leads Puerto Rico to effectively "import" the US currency (the US dollar) and the interest rate determined by the Federal Funds Rate (Rodríguez and Toledo, 2007; Rodríguez, 2016). Nevertheless, other scholars argue that in some dispositions, Puerto Rico appears as a state of the union (like California or New York), while in other dispositions, the island appears as a foreign country (Estrella, 2005).

Given this unique political and economic arrangement, researchers have extensively analyzed the influence of US monetary aggregates as a tool of monetary policy on Puerto Rico's economy (Toledo, 2002; Colón and Martínez, 1999; Alameda, 2000; Rodríguez, 2002). Others have examined the effects of the Federal Funds Rate on Puerto Rico's headline inflation rate and unemployment rate (Rodríguez and Toledo, 2007; Rodríguez, 2017, 2018a). Besides, Puerto Rico not only "imports" the US dollar and interest rates but also absorbs US monetary policy uncertainty through media narratives and continental inflation expectations.

This context raises an important question: What is the nature of the dynamic inter-relationship and influences between US monetary policy uncertainty and inflation expectations on the economy of Puerto Rico? This paper seeks to address this question by examining the dynamic inter-relationships between US monetary policy uncertainty and inflation expectations on the economy of Puerto Rico. The central hypothesis posits that US monetary policy uncertainty and inflation expectations will have a significant impact on Puerto Rico's economy.

Understanding the impact of US monetary policy uncertainty and inflation expectations on Puerto Rico's economy is crucial for local policymakers. For example, suppose this study reveals a significant lag between an increase in US monetary policy uncertainty and a rise in Puerto Rico's unemployment rate. In that case, local officials can utilize this lead time to prepare and implement job creation programs or direct relief before the full impact is felt. The methodological framework employed in this analysis is based on the Vector Autoregression (VAR) approach developed by Toda and Yamamoto (1995).

2. The Effects of Uncertainty and Inflation Expectations

In recent decades, the Federal Reserve System has sought to convey a clear message on policy topics, an increasingly important aspect of its policy work. One clear manifestation of this importance is that, beginning in 1994, the Federal Open Market Committee (FOMC) of the Federal Reserve System started issuing public statements on its monetary policy decisions. Later, in 2012, the FOMC officially adopted a 2% inflation target. This policy reality has led scholars to explore new lines of research. For example, according to Arce-Alfaro and Blagov (2023), the effectiveness of monetary policy depends on the extent to which economic agents can anticipate policy actions. Consequently, much of the existing literature on monetary policy has focused on examining the effects of unanticipated monetary policy shocks. However, as Arce-Alfaro and Blagov (2023) also note, a growing body of research has shifted attention toward understanding how monetary policy unpredictability affects the economy. Within this emerging literature,

there is a broad consensus that increases in monetary policy uncertainty tend to dampen economic activity, raise unemployment, and lower price levels. These effects are consistent with findings suggesting that the consumption channel plays a critical role: risk-averse economic agents tend to postpone consumption in response to higher uncertainty, thereby reducing aggregate demand (Mumtaz and Zanetti, 2013). In this sense, monetary policy uncertainty shocks can be viewed as negative demand shocks that propagate through agents' expectations.

Why are expectations so crucial? In his seminal work, Lucas (1976) emphasized the crucial role of expectations in determining the effectiveness of economic policy. For example, inflation expectations play a key role in wage and price setting (Clarida et al., 2000; Svensson, 2000). Although much of the literature has focused on the effects of unanticipated monetary policy shocks and on how monetary policy unpredictability affects the economy, the literature on inflation expectations has also examined other aspects. For example, the literature on inflation expectations has primarily examined the effects of monetary policy shocks rather than the impact of policy uncertainty (Leduc et al., 2007; Canova and Gambetti, 2009; Leduc and Sill, 2013; Pedersen, 2024). For example, in his study of the Chilean economy, Pedersen (2024) found that updates of inflation expectations depend on the actual inflation rates. Arce-Alfaro and Blagov (2023) make a significant contribution by examining the relationship between inflation expectations and monetary policy uncertainty, arguing that uncertainty is a crucial determinant of inflation expectations. Their results indicate that monetary policy uncertainty reduces both inflation expectations and realized inflation, although this relationship appears to weaken after the Global Financial Crisis of the late 2000s.

3. Puerto Rico's Related Literature

In the current political and institutional context, the macroeconomic conditions of Puerto Rico have been extensively studied in the literature, particularly the dynamics of the inflation rate and the unemployment rate. For example, Toledo (2002) used time series data from June 1966 to March 1999 to study the relationship between the US money supply (M2) and headline inflation in Puerto Rico. The author found that the variables are cointegrated, suggesting that inflation in Puerto Rico is a monetary phenomenon in the long run. Besides, Rodríguez (2004) used a time series with an annual frequency from 1964 to 1997 to study the relationship between the Consumer Price Index (CPI), the real production level, the prime rate, and the money supply (M1). The author found that the variables had the same order of integration, which suggests a stable relationship over time, and the author also found two cointegration vectors (Rodríguez, 2004). Rodríguez and Toledo (2007) examined the effects of the federal funds rate on headline inflation and the unemployment rate in Puerto Rico using a time series from January 1980 to January 2002. The authors found that the federal funds rate anticipated and unanticipated actions precede inflation movements in Puerto Rico.

In another study, Rodríguez (2018a) used a quarterly time series from the first quarter of 1976 to the fourth quarter of 2010 to study the relationship between the Taylor Rule, the unemployment rate, and the headline inflation rate in Puerto Rico. The author found that in the long run, unemployment is declining while inflation is accelerating mainly due to unanticipated expansion of the monetary policy caused by the Taylor Rule. Also, Rodríguez (2017) used monthly time series data to study the relationship between the unemployment rate, the headline inflation rate, and the federal funds rate from January 1976 to December 2010. In this study, the author found that inflation is affected in the first month by the aggregate supply shocks; after the fourth month, the results show various positive and

negative oscillations, and the inflation rate is persistently affected by the impulses of the federal funds rate (Rodríguez, 2017).

Besides, Rodríguez (2007) used quarterly data from the first quarter of 1996 to the fourth quarter of 2005 to study the effect of money growth on headline inflation in Puerto Rico. This author found that the dynamic expansion of money is reflected in prices immediately; however, the unitary effect occurs in ten quarters (approximately). Additionally, the results indicate that Puerto Rican inflation is significantly influenced by its past values and money growth (M1), with money growth being the variable with the most significant influence (Rodríguez, 2007). Quiñones et al. (2013) analyze the causes of headline inflation in Puerto Rico in another study. The authors used a cost-push and demand-pull framework since they used three variables in the sample: the inflation rate, money supply (M2), and oil prices; the sample was from January 1984 to January 2012. The authors found that in the short term, oil prices explain a significant portion of the inflation variation in Puerto Rico. However, the authors also found that, in the long run, inflation appears to be a monetary phenomenon (Quiñones et al., 2013). In another study, Alemar and Rodríguez (2025) utilized a monthly time series from January 2006 to December 2024 to examine the impact of the Federal Funds Rate, the US inflation and unemployment rates, and Brent crude oil prices on Puerto Rico's inflation and unemployment rates. The authors' results suggest that US monetary policy had a more significant effect on Puerto Rico's unemployment than on inflation, as increases in the interest rate generate a lagged increase in the island's unemployment rate, approximately one year later, while the decrease in inflation is practically marginal.

4. Methodological Literature Review

Modern macroeconomic research predominantly employs two methodologies: VAR and Local Projections (LPs) (Sims, 1980; Jordà, 2005). As described by Hamilton (1994), VAR provides a statistical framework to model the dynamic interrelationships among variables. Sims' (1980) seminal work introduced the VAR framework, which treats variables symmetrically and evaluates their mutual influence (Paramanik and Kamaiah, 2014). The VAR framework facilitates various statistical analyses, including Granger Causality Tests, Impulse Response Functions (IRFs), and Variance Decomposition. Causal inference, rooted in multiple disciplines, seeks to identify the effect of one variable on another while controlling for other factors (Heckman, 2008). Belloni et al. (2017) highlight that empirical analyses often examine causal effects, such as the impact of public policies on economic outcomes. In contrast to other approaches, Granger (1969) and Sims (1972) define causality based on predictive power. Specifically, causality in this context refers to whether the past values of one variable and auxiliary variables enhance the predictability of another variable at a future horizon (Dufour and Taamouti, 2010). This predictive framework, known as Granger Causality, is frequently estimated within the VAR system (Romero-Ramírez, 2023).

IRFs quantify the reaction of a variable to a shock in another variable over time. While IRFs originate in signal processing (Jordà, 2023), their application to economics began with Frisch (1933) and gained prominence through the VAR framework introduced by Sims (1980). Variance Decomposition, another tool derived from the VAR framework, measures the extent to which variations in one variable are attributable to shocks in others. Meher et al. (2022) explain that this technique partitions the variance of an outcome variable into components attributed to different sources. Consequently, it identifies whether a shock in one variable significantly contributes to the variability of another (Gorodnichenko and Lee, 2020).

Jordà (2005) introduced LPs as an alternative methodology for analyzing dynamic relationships. LPs involve sequential regressions of future values of an endogenous variable on its lagged values. These regressions can be estimated using ordinary least squares, circumventing the need for asymptotic approximations or complex numerical methods. Importantly, LPs are robust to misspecification of the data-generating process (DGP), which is a potential limitation of the VAR framework. Consequently, LPs are considered a viable alternative to VAR (Jordà, 2005).

While LPs are advantageous in terms of robustness, they are limited in certain aspects. Jordà and Taylor (2024) emphasize that LPs cannot independently uncover causal relationships, as Granger Causality Tests are incompatible with this framework. Nonetheless, IRFs can be computed within the LP framework through sequential projections of lagged variables (Jordà, 2005). Notably, Plagborg-Møller and Wolf (2021) demonstrate that both VAR and LPs yield equivalent IRFs under certain conditions. Gorodnichenko and Lee (2020) further propose a method for estimating Variance Decomposition within the LP framework, although this approach has not been extensively explored. Given these limitations, the VAR framework is preferred in this study for its well-established procedures for estimating Variance Decomposition and its compatibility with Granger Causality analysis.

Before estimating a VAR system, it is essential to examine the dynamic properties of the time series data, particularly the presence of unit roots. Unit root tests, such as the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test (Dickey and Fuller, 1981) and the Phillips-Perron (PP) test (Phillips and Perron, 1988), determine whether the variables have a consistent order of integration. If the variables share the same order of integration, the Johansen Cointegration Test (Johansen, 1991) can identify cointegrated relationships. In the presence of cointegration, a VAR with cointegration restrictions is estimated; otherwise, a standard VAR is used.

If the variables exhibit different orders of integration, the Toda and Yamamoto (1995) framework is employed. This approach modifies the VAR system to accommodate mixed integration orders while maintaining a limiting chi-squared distribution, even when unmet cointegration and stability conditions (Zapata and Rambaldi, 1997). The Toda-Yamamoto framework extends the application of VAR to include Granger Causality Tests and estimates of IRFs and Variance Decomposition (Gylych et al., 2020; Kristoufek, 2022; Romero-Ramírez, 2024).

Additionally, it is essential to note that, given the primary objective of this study is to examine the dynamic interrelationships and mutual influences among the variables, a VAR with cointegration restrictions, a standard VAR, or the Toda-Yamamoto VAR, is most appropriate because, for example a reduced-form VARs treats all variables as endogenous and interdependent, without a priori contemporaneous constraints. In essence, this paper examines how variables evolve together over time and the dynamic response path of the dependent variable after being affected by the other variables in the system. While alternatives such as Structural VAR (SVAR) and Bayesian VAR (BVAR) models often require imposing identifying restrictions derived from specific economic theory (Rodríguez, 2018b) or specific priors (Artis and Zhang, 1990). Besides, these models are usually used when the research considers forecast scenarios, and there are limited observations, which are not the conditions of this paper.

5. Data and Methodology

This study utilizes a dataset spanning from January 1985 to June 2024. The analysis incorporates the following variables: Headline CPI Inflation Rate in Puerto Rico, Unemployment Rate in Puerto Rico, Economic Policy Uncertainty Index: Monetary policy, and University of Michigan: Inflation Expectation (Puerto Rico Department of Labor and Human Resources, 2024; US Bureau of Labor Statistics, 2024;

Baker et al., 2024; University of Michigan, 2024). All variables are transformed into index form, with a base value 100 set for December 2006. To reduce the influence of extreme values, the natural logarithm of each variable is applied prior to estimation. This logarithmic transformation is particularly appropriate given the variability inherent in inflation rates and monetary policy uncertainty.

The Headline CPI Inflation Rate captures overall inflation trends, reflecting price changes across a broad spectrum of goods and services, including volatile components such as food and energy. In contrast, the Unemployment Rate measures the share of unemployed individuals within the total labor force, serving as a critical indicator of labor market conditions. Together, these metrics comprehensively represent Puerto Rico's macroeconomic landscape. In contrast, the Economic Policy Uncertainty Index: Monetary policy quantifies uncertainty surrounding monetary policy discussions, derived from textual analysis of over 2,000 US newspaper articles. Lastly, the University of Michigan: Inflation Expectation variable represents the median anticipated percentage change in prices in the US over the next 12 months. For instance, an inflation expectation of 2% recorded in September indicates that US consumers expect a 2% inflation rate by September of the following year.

The empirical approach begins with the application of unit root tests to assess the dynamic properties of the four variables. Specifically, the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) and Phillips-Perron (PP) tests are employed to determine whether the variables exhibit stationarity. These tests are formally specified in Equations (1) and (2) below:

$$\Delta Y_t = \beta_1 + \beta_2 t + \delta Y_{t-p} + \alpha_i \sum_{i=1}^m \Delta Y_{t-p} + \varepsilon_t \quad (1)$$

$$y_t = \tilde{a}_0 + \tilde{a}_1 y_{t-1} + \tilde{a}_1 \left(t - \frac{T}{2} \right) + \mu_t \quad (2)$$

Both tests incorporate an error term, denoted as (ε_t) and (μ_t) , respectively, alongside a trend component (t) . Both also share a null hypothesis, positing that the series are non-stationary. When the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) and Phillips-Perron (PP) tests indicate that the variables exhibit the same order of integration, applying the Johansen Cointegration Test becomes necessary. This test facilitates the identification of cointegrated equations. The Johansen Cointegration Test comprises two distinct statistical tests: the Trace test and the Maximum Eigenvalue test, which are formally defined in Equations (3) and (4), respectively.

$$J_T = -T \sum_{i=r+1}^n \ln(-\hat{\lambda}_i) \quad (3)$$

$$J_M = -T \ln(-\hat{\lambda}_{r+1}) \quad (4)$$

The primary distinction between these two tests lies in their null and alternative hypotheses. The Trace test evaluates the null hypothesis that there are r cointegrating vectors against the alternative hypothesis of n cointegrating vectors. Conversely, the Maximum Eigenvalue test examines the null

hypothesis of r cointegrating vectors against an alternative hypothesis of $r+1$ cointegrating vectors. If either the Trace test or the Maximum Eigenvalue test detects the presence of cointegrated equations, a VAR model with cointegration restrictions must be estimated. However, if neither test identifies cointegration, a standard VAR model should be estimated, which takes the following functional form:

$$\pi_t = k_\pi + \sum_{i=1}^{12} a_{\pi i} \pi_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^{12} b_{\pi i} u_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^{12} c_{\pi i} \pi^e_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^{12} d_{\pi i} mpu_{t-i} + \varepsilon_{\pi t} \quad (5)$$

$$u_t = k_u + \sum_{i=1}^{12} a_{ui} \pi_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^{12} b_{ui} u_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^{12} c_{ui} \pi^e_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^{12} d_{ui} mpu_{t-i} + \varepsilon_{ut} \quad (6)$$

$$\pi^e_t = k_{\pi^e} + \sum_{i=1}^{12} a_{\pi^e i} \pi_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^{12} b_{\pi^e i} u_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^{12} c_{\pi^e i} \pi^e_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^{12} d_{\pi^e i} mpu_{t-i} + \varepsilon_{\pi^e t} \quad (7)$$

$$mpu_t = k_{mpu} + \sum_{i=1}^{12} a_{mpu i} \pi_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^{12} b_{mpu i} u_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^{12} c_{mpu i} \pi^e_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^{12} d_{mpu i} mpu_{t-i} + \varepsilon_{mpu t} \quad (8)$$

In the previous equations, t is time, π , u , π^e , and mpu are the logarithms of Headline CPI Inflation Rate in Puerto Rico, Unemployment Rate in Puerto Rico, University of Michigan: Inflation Expectation, and Economic Policy Uncertainty Index: Monetary Policy, respectively; the k , a , b , c , a , and d terms are the coefficients that determine how the variables in the system interact. In addition, $\varepsilon_{\pi t}$, ε_{ut} , $\varepsilon_{\pi^e t}$, and $\varepsilon_{mpu t}$ are the error terms that capture the variables' unexplained behavior. It is important to note that in the hypothetical case in which, the ADF and PP tests suggest that the variables do not have a similar order of integration. It will be necessary to use the Toda and Yamamoto (1995) method to estimate the VAR model. Where the correct order of the VAR (k) should be augmented by the maximum order of integration (d_{max}), then the system ($k + d_{max}$) is estimated with the coefficients of the last lagged d_{max} vector being ignored.

6. Results

Tables (1) and (2) summarize the results of the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) and Phillips-Perron (PP) tests, which assess the presence of unit roots in the variables. Prior to estimation, all variables were transformed into their logarithmic forms. The results indicate that the University of Michigan: Inflation Expectation and the Economic Policy Uncertainty Index: Monetary Policy are stationary at their levels, while the Headline CPI Inflation Rate and the Unemployment Rate in Puerto Rico become stationary after first differencing. Since the variables exhibit different orders of integration, conducting the Johansen Cointegration Test is unnecessary. Instead, the analysis employs the Toda and Yamamoto (1995) framework to estimate the VAR model.

Table 1. Unit Root Test – Augmented Dickey-Fuller

Variable	t-Statistic	P-Value	Decision
University of Michigan: Inflation Expectation (π_t^e)			Level for π_t^e
Level	-5.375278	0.0000	
Economic Policy Uncertainty Index: Monetary Policy (mpu_t)			Level for mpu_t
Level	-10.40633	0.0000	
Headline CPI Inflation Rate in Puerto Rico (π_t)			First Difference for π_t
Level	-0.251276	0.9290	
1 st difference	-15.73194	0.0000	
Unemployment Rate in Puerto Rico (u_t)			First Difference for u_t
Level	-0.510921	0.8861	
1 st difference	-10.89248	0.0000	

Source: Author calculations.

Table 2. Unit Root Test – Phillips-Perron

Variable	t-Statistic	P-Value	Decision
University of Michigan: Inflation Expectation (π_t^e)			Level for π_t^e
Level	-6.862287	0.0000	
Economic Policy Uncertainty Index: Monetary Policy (mpu_t)			Level for mpu_t
Level	-10.33756	0.0000	
Headline CPI Inflation Rate in Puerto Rico (π_t)			First Difference for π_t
Level	-0.262613	0.9274	
1 st difference	-17.23815	0.0000	
Unemployment Rate in Puerto Rico (u_t)			First Difference u_t
Level	-0.395412	0.9071	
1 st difference	-10.74133	0.0000	

Source: Author calculations.

The Toda-Yamamoto framework, a modified VAR approach, requires several preparatory steps. First, the optimal lag order must be determined, followed by diagnostic tests to confirm the stability of the system. Table (3) identifies potential optimal lag orders of three, four, five, or six, while Table (4) presents the VAR Residual Serial Correlation LM Test results. Only four and six lag orders pass the LM Test, indicating they are appropriate for the model.

Table 3. VAR Lag Order Selection Criteria

Endogenous variables: $\pi_t, u_t, \pi_t^e, mpu_t$

Exogenous variables: C

Lag	LogL	LR	FPE	AIC	SC	HQ
0	-266.1158	NA	3.75e-05	1.159295	1.194868	1.173295
1	2999.675	6461.500	3.28e-11	-12.78830	-12.61044	-12.71830
2	3111.911	220.1376	2.17e-11	-13.20134	-12.88118	-13.07534
3	3170.961	114.8042	1.81e-11	-13.38610	-12.92366*	-13.20410
4	3219.933	94.37109	1.57e-11	-13.52761	-12.92288	-13.28961*
5	3236.627	31.88374	1.56e-11*	-13.53059*	-12.78357	-13.23659
6	3251.469	28.09202*	1.57e-11	-13.52562	-12.63631	-13.17562

*indicated lag order selected by the criterion. LR: sequential modified LR test statistic (each test at 5% level). FPE: Final prediction error. AIC: Akaike information criterion. SC: Schwarz information criterion. HQ: Hannan-Quinn information criterion.

Source: Author calculations.

Table 4. VAR Residual Serial Correlation LM Test

Null hypothesis: No serial correlation at lag h

Lag	LRE* stat	df	P- Value	Rao F- stat	df	P- Value
1	109.2936	16	0.0000	7.068908	(16, 1393.7)	0.0000
2	113.0159	16	0.0000	7.319503	(16, 1393.7)	0.0000
3	130.9422	16	0.0000	8.535736	(16, 1393.7)	0.0000
4	20.01464	16	0.2196	1.253598	(16, 1393.7)	0.2196
5	39.28807	16	0.0010	2.477820	(16, 1393.7)	0.0010
6	18.74253	16	0.2822	1.173387	(16, 1393.7)	0.2823

Source: Author calculations.

Stability is assessed by examining the roots of the characteristic polynomial, with results shown in Table (5). As no roots lie outside the unit circle, the system satisfies the stability condition required by the Toda-Yamamoto framework. The VAR model, therefore, incorporates the maximum order of integration for each variable. Detailed estimates are provided in the appendix.

Table 5. Roots of Characteristic Polynomial

Endogenous variables: $\pi_t, u_t, \pi_t^e, mpu_t$

Exogenous variables: C

Root	Modulus
0.999542	0.999542
0.985767	0.985767
0.764985	0.764985
0.714847	0.714847
0.595832	0.595832
0.203084	0.203084
-0.119537 - 0.050491i	0.129763
-0.119537 + 0.050491i	0.129763
No root lies outside the unit circle.	
VAR satisfies the stability condition.	

Source: Author calculations.

One of the core results of the study is derived from the Granger Causality Test (Table 6); these results indicate a bi-directional causality relationship between the University of Michigan: Inflation Expectation and both the Headline CPI Inflation Rate and the Unemployment Rate in Puerto Rico. Additionally, the Headline CPI Inflation Rate Granger causes the Unemployment Rate in Puerto Rico. Conversely, the Economic Policy Uncertainty Index: Monetary Policy does not Granger-cause the Headline CPI Inflation Rate or the Unemployment Rate in Puerto Rico but does Granger-cause the University of Michigan: Inflation Expectation. These findings underscore that the University of Michigan: Inflation Expectation significantly influences the movements of the two variables associated with the economy of Puerto Rico.

Table 6. VAR Granger Causality/Block Exogeneity Wald Tests

Dependent variable: Headline CPI Inflation Rate in Puerto Rico (π_t)			
Excluded	Chi-sq	df	P-Value
Unemployment Rate in Puerto Rico (u_t)	2.574015	4	0.6314
University of Michigan: Inflation Expectation (π_t^e)	16.60605	4	0.0023
Economic Policy Uncertainty Index: Monetary Policy (mpu_t)	6.572593	4	0.1603
Dependent variable: Unemployment Rate in Puerto Rico (u_t)			
Excluded	Chi-sq	df	P-Value
Headline CPI Inflation Rate in Puerto Rico (π_t)	9.895871	4	0.0422
University of Michigan: Inflation Expectation (π_t^e)	125.7225	4	0.0000
Economic Policy Uncertainty Index: Monetary Policy (mpu_t)	1.662190	4	0.7976
Dependent variable: University of Michigan: Inflation Expectation (π_t^e)			
Excluded	Chi-sq	df	P-Value
Headline CPI Inflation Rate in Puerto Rico (π_t)	24.72270	4	0.0001
Unemployment Rate in Puerto Rico (u_t)	9.983803	4	0.0407
Economic Policy Uncertainty Index: Monetary Policy (mpu_t)	11.36038	4	0.0228
Dependent variable: Economic Policy Uncertainty Index: Monetary Policy (mpu_t)			
Excluded	Chi-sq	df	P-Value
Headline CPI Inflation Rate in Puerto Rico (π_t)	1.093076	4	0.8954
Unemployment Rate in Puerto Rico (u_t)	3.654656	4	0.4548
University of Michigan: Inflation Expectation (π_t^e)	7.800162	4	0.0992

Source: Author calculations.

Figure (1) illustrates IRFs, showing how variables in the model respond over time to shocks. The left panel of Figure (1) reveals a positive shock to the University of Michigan: Inflation Expectation increases the Headline CPI Inflation Rate in Puerto Rico, with the effect peaking 10 to 20 months after the shock and dissipating after approximately 60 months. Similarly, the right panel indicates a positive shock to the University of Michigan: Inflation Expectation increases the Unemployment Rate in Puerto Rico, with peak effects occurring within the same timeframe and vanishing after 50 months. In contrast, shocks to Puerto Rico's macroeconomic variables have relatively more minor effects on the Economic Policy Uncertainty Index: Monetary Policy. As expected, surprise increases in the Headline CPI Inflation Rate in Puerto Rico also raise the University of Michigan: Inflation Expectation, since Puerto Rico can be considered a representation of a region of the US, and there is evidence in the literature that updates of inflation expectations depend on the actual inflation rates (Pedersen, 2024).

Figure 1. Impulse Response Functions

Source: Author calculations.

Figure (2) presents the Variance Decomposition results, highlighting the relative contributions of each variable to the fluctuations in others. These results suggest that by the final period, the impulses of the University of Michigan: Inflation Expectation explain over 16% and 18% of the variation of the Headline CPI Inflation Rate and the Unemployment Rate in Puerto Rico, respectively. Moreover, these results suggest that the University of Michigan: Inflation Expectation is the third variable (after the Headline CPI Inflation Rate and Unemployment Rate) that explains the higher percentage of the Headline CPI Inflation Rate variation in Puerto Rico. Furthermore, the University of Michigan: Inflation Expectation is the second variable (after the Unemployment Rate) that explains the higher percentage of the variation of the Unemployment Rate in Puerto Rico.

While, for the same period, the impulses of the Headline CPI Inflation Rate and the Unemployment Rate in Puerto Rico explain over 22% and 23% of the variation of the University of Michigan: Inflation Expectation, respectively. This was an expected result, since Puerto Rico is considered part of the US and, as mentioned before, there is evidence that inflation expectations updates depend on the actual inflation rate (Pedersen, 2024). In contrast, by the final period, the impulses of the Economic Policy Uncertainty Index: Monetary Policy explain less than 2.11% and 1.60% of the variation of the Headline CPI Inflation Rate and the Unemployment Rate in Puerto Rico, respectively. Besides, Figure (2) shows

that by the final period, the impulses of the Headline CPI Inflation Rate and the Unemployment Rate in Puerto Rico explain less than 1.4% and 9% of the variation of the Economic Policy Uncertainty Index: Monetary Policy, respectively.

Figure 2. Variance Decomposition

Source: Author calculations.

In summary, the Granger Causality Test, the IRFs, and the Variance Decomposition results suggest that the median anticipated percentage change in US prices over the next 12 months significantly affects the movements of the Headline CPI Inflation Rate and the Unemployment Rate in Puerto Rico. The uncertainty surrounding monetary policy discussions, as extracted from over 2,000 US newspaper sources, does not significantly affect the two variables associated with the economy of Puerto Rico. Besides, these results could also imply that the economy of Puerto Rico effectively "imports" inflation expectations from the continental US, while it does not "import" monetary policy uncertainty.

7. Concluding Remarks

This paper examines the relationship between the Headline CPI Inflation Rate and the Unemployment Rate in Puerto Rico with US monetary policy uncertainty and Inflation Expectations. Utilizing a sample from January 1985 to June 2024, the analysis employs a VAR model following the methodology proposed by Toda and Yamamoto (1995). The Granger Causality Test reveals that the Headline CPI Inflation Rate and the Unemployment Rate in Puerto Rico have a bi-directional Granger causality relationship with the University of Michigan: Inflation Expectation, which measures US inflation expectations. However, no causality is found between the Economic Policy Uncertainty Index: Monetary Policy and the Headline CPI Inflation Rate or the Unemployment Rate in Puerto Rico.

Impulse Response Functions (IRFs) indicate that unexpected increases in the University of Michigan: Inflation Expectation lead to a higher Headline CPI Inflation Rate in Puerto Rico, with the peak effects materializing between 10 and 20 months post-shock. These effects gradually dissipate, converging to zero approximately 60 months after the shock. Similarly, surprise increases in the University of Michigan: Inflation Expectation results in a higher Unemployment Rate in Puerto Rico, with peak effects occurring

within the same time frame. Notably, the Unemployment Rate's responses to shocks from other variables in the system exhibit oscillations that subside around 50 months post-impact. Furthermore, shocks to Puerto Rico's macroeconomic variables exert only minimal influence on the Economic Policy Uncertainty Index: Monetary Policy. As anticipated, unexpected increases in the Headline CPI Inflation Rate in Puerto Rico also raise the University of Michigan Inflation Expectation, reflecting Puerto Rico's status as a de facto region of the US, since evidence suggests that inflation expectations update depends on actual inflation rates.

Variance Decomposition results further underscore the significance of the University of Michigan: Inflation Expectation. By the final period, its impulses account for over 16% and 18% of the variation in the Headline CPI Inflation Rate and the Unemployment Rate in Puerto Rico, respectively. The findings also reveal that the University of Michigan: Inflation Expectation ranks as the third most influential variable (following the Headline CPI Inflation Rate and the Unemployment Rate) in explaining variations in the Headline CPI Inflation Rate. Additionally, it emerges as the second most influential variable (after the Unemployment Rate) in explaining variations in the Unemployment Rate. Conversely, during the same period, the impulses of the Headline CPI Inflation Rate and the Unemployment Rate in Puerto Rico collectively account for over 22% and 23% of the variation in the University of Michigan: Inflation Expectation, respectively. These outcomes align with expectations, given that Puerto Rico is a de facto region of the US. In stark contrast, by the final period, the impulses of the Economic Policy Uncertainty Index: Monetary Policy contributes less than 2.11% and 1.60% to the variation in the Headline CPI Inflation Rate and the Unemployment Rate in Puerto Rico, respectively. Moreover, by the final period, the impulses of the Headline CPI Inflation Rate and the Unemployment Rate in Puerto Rico explain less than 1.4% and 9% of the variation in the Economic Policy Uncertainty Index: Monetary Policy, respectively.

A principal limitation of this study lies in the availability and quality of data. As highlighted, key variables such as monetary policy uncertainty and inflation expectations are not measured or published specifically for Puerto Rico. Additionally, the data available are often released with significant delays, subject to substantial revisions, and, in some instances, may be questioned on other grounds. A prominent example of these limitations pertains to price data; until 2008, the Puerto Rico Department of Labor and Human Resources utilized a basket of goods and services surveyed in 1977 to estimate the CPI (Bram et al., 2008). The current basket of goods and services was surveyed between 1999 and 2003. Given these changes, Rodríguez (2016) studied the variation in the autoregressive structure of inflation in Puerto Rico due to a methodological change in the CPI. According to the results, the series of inflation, with the new methodology, shows a more stable behavior than the previous one, but it is close to having a unit root process.

However, it is noteworthy that the Puerto Rico Department of Labor and Human Resources is currently updating the basket of goods and services used for CPI estimation. From a policy perspective, enhancing the quantity and quality of economic data on the island is imperative. Policymakers should allocate adequate budgetary resources to address these deficiencies. Moreover, local policymakers in Puerto Rico must closely monitor the influence of US inflation expectations on the Headline CPI Inflation Rate and the Unemployment Rate, as these variables are pivotal to the island's economic performance. Given our results, which show that US inflation expectations increase the Headline CPI Inflation Rate and that the Unemployment Rate and its effects peak 10 to 20 months after the initial shock, local officials in Puerto Rico have some time to implement job-creation programs or direct relief before the full impact is felt. Future studies could consider examine the same relationships as in this paper, but by "breaking" the time series into different periods and studied them separately, for example: the Puerto

Rico's golden age associated with the second half of the 20th century, the collapse and economic stagnation between 2006 and 2017, the period of natural disasters from 2017 to 2020 and the reconstruction from 2021 to 2024. In essence, our paper should be considered just the start of the conversation on this topic, since there are other factors to consider that could yield additional insights into the relationship between Puerto Rico's macroeconomic dynamics, continental inflation expectations, and monetary policy uncertainty.

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APPENDIX

Table A1. VAR Estimates
Standard errors in () & t-statistics in []

	π_t	u_t	π_t^e	mpu_t
$\pi_t(-1)$	1.185284 (0.04905) [24.1636]	-0.009399 (0.14868) [-0.06322]	5.178127 (1.31062) [3.95089]	-2.656505 (4.82084) [-0.55105]
$\pi_t(-2)$	-0.404765 (0.07476) [-5.41386]	0.033528 (0.22661) [0.14796]	-3.455881 (1.99762) [-1.73000]	1.297339 (7.34782) [0.17656]
$\pi_t(-3)$	0.193823 (0.07659) [2.53081]	0.352137 (0.23213) [1.51701]	2.118214 (2.04626) [1.03516]	4.845820 (7.52673) [0.64381]
$\pi_t(-4)$	0.012803 (0.07481) [0.17114]	-0.160593 (0.22674) [-0.70828]	-2.503521 (1.99876) [-1.25254]	-4.840208 (7.35199) [-0.65835]
$u_t(-1)$	-0.013172 (0.01530) [-0.86089]	1.587564 (0.04637) [34.2335]	-0.403241 (0.40881) [-0.98638]	2.677737 (1.50371) [1.78075]
$u_t(-2)$	0.018451 (0.02911) [0.63387]	-0.390517 (0.08823) [-4.42634]	0.641218 (0.77774) [0.82446]	-4.599794 (2.86075) [-1.60790]
$u_t(-3)$	-0.005741 (0.02700) [-0.21267]	-0.379469 (0.08182) [-4.63772]	-0.830082 (0.72129) [-1.15082]	2.460052 (2.65312) [0.92723]
$u_t(-4)$	-0.014491 (0.02529) [-0.57299]	0.057708 (0.07665) [0.75287]	0.177312 (0.67570) [0.26241]	-0.795283 (2.48543) [-0.31998]
$\pi_t^e(-1)$	0.006458 (0.00182) [3.53897]	-0.008398 (0.00553) [-1.51828]	0.680749 (0.04876) [13.9614]	0.192007 (0.17935) [1.07057]
$\pi_t^e(-2)$	-0.000559 (0.00218) [-0.25717]	0.028785 (0.00659) [4.36539]	-0.112293 (0.05813) [-1.93180]	-0.404115 (0.21381) [-1.89003]
$\pi_t^e(-3)$	-0.001802 (0.00220) [-0.81723]	-0.070206 (0.00668) [-10.5075]	0.213939 (0.05890) [3.63224]	0.402690 (0.21665) [1.85871]
$\pi_t^e(-4)$	-9.71E-05 (0.00250) [-0.03889]	0.027197 (0.00756) [3.59549]	-0.125756 (0.06668) [-1.88591]	0.104272 (0.24527) [0.42512]

$mpu_t(-1)$	-0.000435 (0.00048) [-0.90529]	0.000504 (0.00146) [0.34630]	-0.023434 (0.01283) [-1.82591]	0.554390 (0.04721) [11.7435]
$mpu_t(-2)$	-0.000898 (0.00055) [-1.63300]	-0.001482 (0.00167) [-0.88921]	-0.018432 (0.01469) [-1.25465]	0.086100 (0.05404) [1.59336]
$mpu_t(-3)$	0.000450 (0.00055) [0.81654]	0.000604 (0.00167) [0.36199]	0.026405 (0.01472) [1.79422]	-0.053772 (0.05413) [-0.99335]
$mpu_t(-4)$	0.000167 (0.00055) [0.30388]	0.001495 (0.00166) [0.89855]	0.015265 (0.01466) [1.04102]	-0.043454 (0.05394) [-0.80567]
C	0.021007 (0.01313) [1.60044]	0.000880 (0.03978) [0.02211]	0.881626 (0.35071) [2.51382]	2.513025 (1.29002) [1.94805]
$\pi_t(-5)$	0.009926 (0.04947) [0.20066]	-0.215656 (0.14993) [-1.43842]	-1.323936 (1.32165) [-1.00173]	1.104887 (4.86140) [0.22728]
$u_t(-5)$	0.012280 (0.01399) [0.87810]	0.124474 (0.04239) [2.93655]	0.417849 (0.37366) [1.11825]	0.117816 (1.37444) [0.08572]
$\pi_t^e(-5)$	-0.001260 (0.00197) [-0.63956]	0.020419 (0.00597) [3.42083]	0.119261 (0.05262) [2.26650]	0.017689 (0.19355) [0.09139]
$mpu_t(-5)$	-0.000261 (0.00048) [-0.54165]	0.000176 (0.00146) [0.12051]	0.010692 (0.01286) [0.83159]	0.102777 (0.04729) [2.17318]
R-squared	0.999595	0.997685	0.692089	0.434039
Adj. R-squared	0.999577	0.997582	0.678343	0.408773
Sum sq. resids	0.009719	0.089282	6.938120	93.87109
S.E. equation	0.004658	0.014117	0.124446	0.457748
F-statistic	55330.49	9654.308	50.34832	17.17871
Log likelihood	1863.438	1343.376	322.6004	-288.2466
Akaike AIC	-7.856878	-5.639132	-1.286143	1.318749
Schwarz SC	-7.671030	-5.453284	-1.100295	1.504597
Mean dependent	4.535434	4.788064	4.652363	6.122715
S.D. dependent	0.226531	0.287077	0.219425	0.595319
Determinant resid covariance (dof adj.)		1.29E-11		
Determinant resid covariance		1.07E-11		
Log likelihood		3260.900		
Akaike information criterion		-13.54755		
Schwarz criterion		-12.80415		
Number of coefficients		84		

Source: Author calculations.